

AN INVESTIGATION OF STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN CFRP IOSIPESCU SHEAR TEST SPECIMEN

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to investigate the stress distribution in unidirectional carbon-fibre composite Iosipescu shear test specimens and to evaluate its effect on intralaminar shear strength and shear modulus measurements. Photoelastic shear stress fringe patterns obtained from the Iosipescu specimens show a strong similarity to the numerically determined von Mises stress contours. Using correction factors to account for the non-uniform shear stress distribution in the Iosipescu specimen, the actual shear moduli can be established from the experimental data. The Iosipescu shear test also provides a reasonable estimate of the shear strength. Apparent shear strength data obtained from the Iosipescu shear test and the results from the thin-walled hoop-wound tubes tested in torsion were in good agreement.

INTRODUCTION

Stress distribution in the Iosipescu shear test specimen is dependent on the orthotropy ratio, fibre orientation, notch geometry and the loading boundary conditions[1-5]. Numerous finite element analyses and photoelastic studies[1-8] show that the shear stress distribution along the notch root axis of Iosipescu specimens is not uniform. It has been suggested[3] that it is necessary to apply correction factors to account for the difference between applied average shear stress and the actual shear stress, particularly in the case of materials with a high orthotropy ratio. These studies have also shown that the shear stress concentration and normal stresses at the notch roots introduce difficulties in determining shear strength. Kumosa and Hull[5] showed that the shear stress concentration factor K_t at the notch roots, defined as the ratio of the shear at the notch root to the shear stress in the specimen centre, can be expressed in terms of the orthotropy ratio and fibre orientation as:

$$K_t = A (E_{11}/E_{22})^{1/4} \quad (1)$$

where A is a numerical factor dependent on the loading boundary conditions.

This implies that the average shear stress $\bar{\tau}$ calculated from the total vertical force applied to the Iosipescu specimen divided by the cross-sectional area between the notch roots, is usually not representative of the stress at the specimen centre. To determine the shear modulus and shear strength of the composite, it is necessary to account for the non-uniform shear stress distribution and normal stresses present in the Iosipescu specimen.

In this paper, shear properties of unidirectional carbon/epoxy and carbon/PEEK composites are determined using the Iosipescu shear test. A combined experimental and numerical investigation is performed to analyse the influence of stress distribution in the Iosipescu specimen on the measured shear strength and moduli of the tested materials. Finite element analysis was used to evaluate the shear stress distribution within the specimen for two different fibre orientations. Comparative photoelastic and numerical results are presented to confirm that the loading conditions assumed by finite element analysis are very close to the experimental loading configuration.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The intralaminar shear strength and shear modulus was measured for 40-ply unidirectional AS4/3501-6, XAS 914C and T300B R23 carbon/epoxy and APC-2 carbon/PEEK using the Iosipescu shear test technique. In addition, thin-walled hoop-wound T300B R23 carbon/epoxy tubes were tested in torsion, to

provide reference shear data. Iosipescu specimens were cut with fibres parallel to the specimen longitudinal axis $[0^\circ]$ and perpendicular to this axis $[90^\circ]$. The dimensions and fibre orientations of the specimen are shown in Fig. 1. A 90° angle notch was cut with faces oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the fibre direction, to a depth of 20% of the specimen width. The notch root radius was $\sim 40\mu\text{m}$.

Fig.1 Iosipescu Shear Test Configuration

The specimens were tested at a cross-head speed of 1mm/min. A Kyowa (KFC-1-D16-11) 90° biaxial rosette was bonded to the centre of the specimen in the area between the notches. The gauges were aligned at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the specimen axis and were 1mm long. Tests were performed in a universally adaptable In-plane Biaxial Stress Fixture[8]. This test fixture is capable of testing Iosipescu specimens in either shear or a combination of shear, transverse tension and compressive loadings.

Hoop-wound tubes were fabricated from T300B R23 carbon/epoxy with a nominal wall thickness of 2mm, an internal diameter of 50mm, a gauge length of 125mm and an overall length of 225mm. The tubes were subjected to pure torsional loading at a constant rotation rate of $2.5^\circ/\text{min}$. Shear strain was recorded using a 90° biaxial rosette oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the fibre direction, bonded at the centre of the gauge length.

Stress distributions were determined by finite element methods using the PAFEC system. The loading boundary conditions applied to the finite element model were chosen to simulate the loading configuration originally proposed by Iosipescu with two force couples applied to the Iosipescu specimen (Fig.1)[7]. This is known as the force-couple condition. A comparative photoelastic study was performed on $[0^\circ]$ and $[90^\circ]$ specimens to demonstrate that the assumed loading boundary conditions were representative of the actual experimental configuration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparative photoelastic and numerical studies revealed that the general features of the normalised von Mises stress contours for both $[0^\circ]$ and $[90^\circ]$ specimens showed good qualitative agreement with the isochromatic fringes, prior to the onset of initial splitting at the notch roots (Figs. 2 and 3).

Fig.2 $[0^\circ]$ Iosipescu Specimen
 Left - Isochromatic Fringes
 Right - Normalised von Mises Contours

Fig. 3 [90°] Iosipescu Specimen
 Left - Isochromatic Fringes
 Right - Normalised von Mises Contours

The mechanical response of both [0°] and [90°] Iosipescu specimens was initially linear, and the onset of non-linearity occurred between 40 and 50% of the apparent shear strength. This was followed by a region of extensive non-linearity before onset of failure. Failure of [0°] Iosipescu specimens initiated at the notch roots with two approximately symmetric cracks (Fig.4) propagating parallel to the fibres on the opposite sides to the inner loading points. Axial splitting was associated with the occurrence of two successive load drops of the order of 100N magnitude on the force-displacement diagram. A shear stress concentration at the notch root nucleates failure, with crack growth in the principal tensile stress plane being prevented by the aligned fibres. After axial splitting, two damage zones, at approximately 80° to the crack planes (shear bands) appear with barely detectable influence on the shear stress-strain response (Fig. 4). Numerous short interfacial cracks and extensive fibre bending occur. Damage zones extend towards the test specimen centre, with fracture locus corresponding to the maximum shear contour within the region[5].

Fig.4 Failed [0°] Iosipescu Specimen
 Left - Longitudinal Axial Splitting
 Right - Damage Zone

Axial splitting and damage zone formation (secondary failure) can be regarded as intralaminar failures. These two events were followed by interply failure, initiated at the inner loading points. Compressive stresses in the loading zones (Figs. 3 and 4) in combination with high shear stresses tend to suppress intralaminar shear failure, with the final failure mode being essentially compressive buckling or yielding.

Failure of [90°] Iosipescu specimens usually initiated in the vicinity of the upper notch with crack propagation parallel to the fibres. The failure was catastrophic and resulted in complete separation of the specimen.

Shear modulus G_{12} was determined from the linear region of the shear stress-strain curve. The measured shear moduli for [0°] specimens G_{12L}^* and [90°] specimens G_{12T}^* are given in Table 1. From the finite element analysis[7], correction factors 0.84 and 1.13 were determined for G_{12L} and G_{12T} respectively, to account for the non-uniform shear stress distribution along the notch root axis. The corrected shear moduli agree to within 8% of theoretical predictions based on the Halpin-Tsai equations (Table 1). It is apparent from the results in Table 1 that there is good agreement between the shear modulus obtained from the hoop-wound tubes tested in torsion and the corrected shear moduli from the Iosipescu tests.

TABLE 1
EXPERIMENTAL, NUMERICALLY
CORRECTED AND PREDICTED SHEAR MODULI (GPa)

SPECIMEN	MEASURED*		CORRECTED AVERAGE		PREDICTED
	G_{12L}	G_{12T}	G_{12L}	G_{12T}	G_{12}
AS4/3501-6	7.48±0.05	5.87±0.20	6.28	6.63	6.15
XAS914C	6.31±0.25	5.01±0.41	5.30	5.66	5.70
T300B R23	5.38±0.23	4.44±0.27	4.52	5.02	4.66
APC-2	6.48±0.55	5.05±0.19	5.75	5.71	5.46
T300B R23	HOOP-WOUND TUBES				$G_{12} = 5.06±0.36$

Determination of shear strength τ_{12}^u for [0°] Iosipescu specimens is difficult because of the following: (i) the presence of axial bending stresses and transverse normal stresses in addition to a shear stress concentration at the notch roots; (ii) non-linearity of the shear stress-strain response[4,5,8]. The finite element analysis performed neglects the effects of creep and plasticity, and assumes a linear-elastic response to failure. For $E_{11}/E_{22} = 14.2$, the predicted stress concentration factor K_t was 2.07 and 0.55 for [0°] and [90°] respectively. The effect of inelastic shear behaviour was to reduce the stress concentration[1]. This non-linear response was caused by creep, plasticity and accumulation of micro-damage at the notch roots[8]. Axial splitting produced stress relief at the notch roots[5] and tended to promote a more uniform shear stress distribution within the specimen mid-section (Fig.5).

The average secondary stress at failure measured for T300B R23 carbon/epoxy was in excellent agreement with the apparent shear strength determined from the torsion tests. (Table 2). Lower failure stresses were recorded for [90°] specimens. The discrepancy between the [0°] and [90°] apparent shear strength values was probably the result of significant normal tensile stress components present at the notch roots of [90°] specimens.

Fig.5 [0°] Iosipescu Specimen Secondary Failure - Isochromatic Fringes.

TABLE 2
MEASURED STRESS AT FAILURE (MPa)

SPECIMEN	1ST AXIAL SPLIT [0°]	SECONDARY [0°]	ULTIMATE [0°]	ULTIMATE [90°]
AS4/3501-6	69.12±0.55	75.19±0.62	81.30±3.76	58.69±1.46
XAS 914C	75.11±1.84	81.87±2.06	89.98±1.81	62.02±1.86
T300B R23	69.11±2.11	76.02±2.38	84.96±2.46	58.51±2.53
APC-2	71.52±0.41	76.53±0.45	86.36±3.24	71.01±1.29
T300B R23	HOOP-WOUND TUBES		75.25±3.29	

CONCLUSIONS

1. Photoelastic results confirm that the loading boundary conditions assumed in the finite element analysis approximate the experimental loading configuration.
2. Experimental shear moduli when corrected to account for the non-uniform shear stress distribution in the gauge section were in good agreement with the corresponding torsion data and theoretical predictions.
3. Axial splitting tends to promote a more uniform stress distribution in the gauge section.
4. Shear strength results for the Iosipescu specimens with [0°] fibre orientation and corresponding strength data for the hoop-wound tubes suggest that the stress concentration factor K_t at failure is close to unity

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